

Effectiveness of Teaching Practices for Primary Students in Inclusive Classroom

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Abstract

A unique strategy for educating children with challenges and learning differences alongside typically developing students is known as inclusive education (IE). It indicates that all learners those with and those without disabilities can learn alongside one another by having access to standard school resources and a community learning environment with the necessary infrastructure of support services. To integrate disabled students into the system of regular education, there have been attempts on a global scale. We must consider and include children with special needs in ordinary classrooms if we want to achieve truly inclusive education. Particularly considering the difficulties these students have, participating and learning in the classroom. Teachers are becoming more and more aware of the importance of valuing each child as an individual as general education classrooms contain an increasing number of diverse students. Hence, this study is important from the point of view to better educate general education teachers about strategies to teach students with special needs to attain the desirable optimum results with these methods.

Keywords: Teaching Practices, Primary Students, Inclusive Classroom, Inclusive Education.

Introduction:

"If a child can't learn the way we teach maybe we should teach the way they learn"

- Ignacio Estrada

Every child, regardless of religion, caste, gender, language, social or ethnic origin, or disability, has the fundamental right to an education. In the present day, inclusive education is essential for removing obstacles and successfully integrating all marginalised children into the mainstream educational system because every child should have an equal opportunity to receive an education. There should be an increased effort to universalize education irrespective of any disabilities suffered by the child. Children with disabilities need to attend mainstream schools without being treated differently from children without impairments. They shouldn't be isolated, held in small spaces within special schools, or denied equality in society. Additionally, these children should be entitled to high-quality education and facilities, as well as equitable access to learning opportunities in regular schools alongside other children.

Present Scenario of Inclusive Education In India:

As per the census, 10% of the world's population lives with a disability, and 80% of these people with disabilities live in developing countries (Chatterjee, 2015).

An estimated nearly 50% of children with disabilities are not in school. Estimated eight million children out of school in India (Sarthaka Singh, 2020).

India has been working towards legalizing the acceptance of the child with disability through its Acts and Policies over the decades. Yet this has been slow. NCERT with the references of the documents

framed by UNICEF has ultimately lead to the development of the National Curriculum Framework for school Education (2005), a contemporary guiding document for School Education in India.

Some of the contemporary developments in the recent decades that have shaped the concept of inclusion in India are:

- 2006: The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities is adopted and ratified by India; however, they did not adopt or ratify the protocol. Article 24 of the Convention discusses the importance of inclusion.
- 2006: The National Policy for People with Disabilities changes special schools into resource centers for people with disabilities and teachers. It also attempts to bridge the service gap between rural and urban areas by creating more District Disability and Rehabilitation Centers.
- 2008: Inclusive Education of the Disabled at the Secondary Stage (IEDSS) replacing the 1974 IEDC.
- 2009: The Right to Education Act, which was originally drafted in 2005, was not passed until 2009, and put into full effect in 2010. The supreme court upheld the constitutionality of the act in 2012. This act was not disability specific, but rather included people with disabilities.

According to the World Bank Report (2007), in India 38 per cent of the children with disabilities in the age group 6-13 years are out of school and even for children attending school, the school attendance is never more than 70% for boys and 66% for girls (Dr. Renu Malaviya, Dr. Tulika Talwar).

With the new Education Policy (NEP 2020) Indian education enters into the era of inclusive education where children with disabilities will not be denied school admission under any circumstances. NEP will provide hand holding to disabled children and lead them to the best schools, which under no condition can say "no" to the child with disabilities to be a part of the education system (Rajeev Bhatt, March 24, 2022).

Significance of The Research

With the majority of today's special education students, we are not dealing with students with physical or mental incompetence, we are dealing with children who do not learn what we teach or do not like the way we teach it. So, we have to improve what we teach and make it usable to students and we have to improve how we teach it. (Dr. William Glasser)

In its broadest sense, inclusive education as a strategy aims to meet the educational requirements of every child and adolescent with an emphasis on those who are most at risk of marginalization and exclusion.

It indicates that all students, including those with and without disabilities, will be able to learn together due to access to educational institutions like schools and community centers that provide a reliable system of support services. The most frequently included students are those whose physical impairments have little impact on their academic performance, students with all types of mild impairments, and students whose impairments require only minimal specialist services.

This study aims to provide improved social development and academic outcomes for all learners. It leads to the development of social skills and better social interactions because learners are exposed to real environment in which they have to interact with other learners, each one having unique characteristics, interest and abilities.

Results suggests that, after implementing the innovative teaching practices there is significant progress toward individualized goals, which encourages future research.

This is the significance of this study and it will aim to add a qualitative value to the concept on Inclusive Education.

Objectives of The Study

1. To implement different teaching practices for primary students in Inclusive Classroom.
2. To test the effectiveness of teaching practices for primary students in Inclusive Classroom.

Methodology

Experimental Method:

The present study is an experimental research which is followed by testing of special strategies of teaching on learning to the students in inclusive classroom. Experimental research tries to establish 'a systematic and logical association between manipulated factors and observed effects' (Lokesh Koul, 1997 p. 466). Advantage of using experimental research is that it helps researcher to control the variables, provide insight into the method of instruction and determines what would be best for the population. The investigator has used this method so as to know whether strategies used for teaching the primary students with disability of Lexicon School in inclusive classroom has any effect or not; and whether the strategies would be applicable in classroom teaching in this area.

Experimental design is regarded as blueprint of the procedure which helps the researcher to test the hypotheses by finding valid conclusion about the relationship between independent and dependent variables. In this study, the independent variables are the teaching practices; while dependent variables are the test scores of the students.

Population and Sample

At present inclusive education is being implemented in 30 schools in Pune City. Therefore, the population of the study comprise of primary students with and without special needs of all Inclusive Schools.

Thirty students has been taken from the students of class V studying in The Lexicon School, Hadapsar, as the sample of the study, since this school is well accessible to the investigator. This school was selected purposively, keeping in view the willingness of the principal and staffs to co-operate with the investigator in conducting the research project.

Measurement Tool

In order to collect data from the students of class V studying in The Lexicon School, Hadapsar, achievement test was developed by the researcher. To test the effectiveness of the teaching strategies on the learning of primary students the researcher conducted achievement test as pre-test and post-test. Thirty students of class V studying in Lexicon School, Hadapsar, were given a pre-assessment test on "Multiples and Factors" "Fractions" and "Decimals" to check their previous knowledge in Mathematics. There were 15 questions in total for the pre-assessment test, out of which questions were given from the chapter "Multiples and Factors" and the rest was equally distributed from the other two chapters. After implementing the special teaching strategies with the traditional method on the students, they were asked to solve the sums from post-assessment test. There were same number of questions and distribution of marks was same in the postassessment question paper.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

Table-1: shows the results of the pre-test conducted before commencing the program.

Candidate Sr No	Pre-test Marks	Candidate Sr No	Pre-test Marks
1	19	16	25
2	19	17	23
3	14	18	23
4	15	19	18
5	19	20	17
6	18	21	20
7	18	22	24
8	23	23	24
9	22	24	23
10	23	25	24
11	16	26	18
12	25	27	18
13	25	28	17

14	22	29	15
15	22	30	20

Figure-1

Figure - 2

As shown in the figure 2 there was a wide range in performance on all questions. The researcher also wanted to determine the percentage of students who showed basic awareness of the skills (**i.e., performance of at least 50% correct**) before beginning the online coursework. As shown in the figure approximately 57% of the students showed basic awareness of the skills being tested for.

Table-2: shows the results of the post-test conducted after commencing the program

Candidate Sr. No.	Post-test Marks	Candidate Sr No.	Pos-test Marks
1	24	16	28
2	22	17	28
3	19	18	29
4	20	19	21
5	23	20	22
6	21	21	23
7	22	22	25
8	27	23	28
9	25	24	29
10	27	25	29
11	20	26	21
12	28	27	20
13	29	28	21
14	26	29	20
15	27	30	22

Figure-3

Figure-4

As shown in the figure 4 there the range in performance on all questions seems to be much stabilized and consistent. The researcher also wanted to determine the percentage of students who showed mastery of the skills (i.e., performance of at least 75% correct) after completing the online coursework. As shown in the figure approximately 49% of the students showed mastery of the skills being tested for.

Cumulative Data Analysis

Figure - 5

Above figure shows that the performance of all students has improved after completion of the online programme.

Major Findings

Based on the calculated value of $t = - 4.557$ following conclusions can be safely drawn:

1. Negative sign for the value of "t" means it's a one tail test. Effectively implying that the post-test scores are more than the pre-test scores.
2. Degree of freedom = N-1
= 30 -1
= 29
3. Table "t" value = 1.699
4. Calculated "t" value 4.557 is greater than table "t" value 1.699.

Discussion

The aim of the study was to determine if there was an improvement on the learning of primary students after implementing online programme. Assessment was taken to check their overall progress. When evaluating the students' progress at the end of the course, significant improvements in performance were found among the students. Based on the data analysis and findings, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the directional hypothesis which suggests that the online programme based on inclusive teaching practices is effective in improving knowledge and application skills of the primary students in inclusive classroom.

Conclusion:

The development of cognitive and social skills in students that are required in today's school education system is ensured by inclusive teaching approaches, which encourage meaningful and accessible learning for all students.

This study provided the base to improve and enhance the learning input of students with special needs and thus leading towards successful inclusion in all dimensions. This inclusive teaching strategy benefits at the Individual level and has provided a sense of positive interdependence between students, improves interpersonal and social skills and for accountability. The study results represent that Inclusive Teaching strategy is a learning paradigm and it assures that every member in the group has learned something. There is no doubt that inclusive teaching methods have a wider range of potential for learning and can significantly aid in the achievement of the country's inclusive growth and development goal.

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